

Festschrift for Nina F. Thornhill

Editorial

It is a great pleasure to serve as editors for the Festschrift on the occasion of the retirement of Prof. Nina F. Thornhill or short – Nina – as most contributors call her. Nina is the ABB/RAEng Professor of Process Automation at Imperial College London.

Education and professional career

Receiving her undergraduate degree in Physics in 1976 from Oxford University shows how extraordinary Nina is. Getting into Oxford University is and always has been difficult. In 1973, there were 25 colleges for men but only five for women. Thus, it was five times harder for women to get in than for men.

After completing her BA in Physics at Oxford at St. Hilda's in 1976, Nina joined ICI, which was for much of its history Britain's largest manufacturer of chemicals and pharmaceuticals. She left ICI in 1983 to study for a Master's in Control Systems at Imperial College London. She subsequently briefly worked for British Aerospace as a control systems engineer.

Nina became a member of the faculty in the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering at University College London (UCL) in 1984 where she worked for 23 years, first as a lecturer, then senior lecturer in 1991, jumping up straight to full Professor in 2003 and eventually Deputy Head of Department in 2006.

Her excellence in research combines industrial relevance with academic preeminence, and was recognized by the Royal Academy of Engineering (RAE) and ABB who funded the chair of Process Automation at Imperial College for her in 2007. She became made a Fellow of the Royal Academy in 2010.

In August 2019, Nina received the Nordic Process Control Award, celebrating her achievements in research over the course of her career.

Academic Contributions

Nina researched in data analytics long before the hype around big data, data science and artificial intelligence. As early as 1984 she was working on data-driven monitoring of fermentation processes, and it is important to keep in mind that data analytics was much harder then: events of that year include the introduction of the 3.5 inch floppy disk and the foundation of Mathworks.

With over 190 publications authored by her, or co-authored, Nina spearheaded the development of time series analysis methods in directions of industrial value. One of the notable areas, which featured early in her research interests, was control loop performance assessment, valve stiction analysis, oscillation detection and root-cause diagnosis. Building on this expertise, she later identified opportunities to advance plant-wide data analysis, which included country-wide power transmission grids and analyses crossing the chemical, mechanical and electrical subsystems in a plant.

Despite her proven expertise in the desirable area of data analytics, Nina's work approach is always one of critical questioning and not jumping on bandwagons. Quoting her: "You can find anything you want in data, but whether it is

meaningful requires one to understand the processes behind the analysed system.” Nina always keeps the big picture in mind and is driven by solving real problems, which gives her a good intuition for what works and what doesn’t. A keen collaborator, Nina has developed extensive research links around the Globe.

Contributions beyond Research

Nina’s impact reaches well beyond her contribution to research content. She expertly coordinated large EU projects as part of the FP7 and EU Horizon 2020 programme. As the ABB Chair of Process Automation she served on ABB’s Jürgen Dormann Foundation board which awards scholarships to engineering students in different parts of the world. Nina served on the ABB Hubertus von Grünberg Award committee which awards a \$300,000 grant to a research student. At Imperial College, Nina contributed significantly to engineering education by setting up the MSc program in Process Automation, Instrumentation and Control of which she was the director. She served as the director of undergraduate studies at the department of chemical engineering. Over her entire career, Nina was involved in industry bodies such as the IChemE and IET (formerly the IEE) where she acted in different roles, dedicating time and insight to the UK automation community.

Sabbaticals and Secondments

The special nature of Nina’s career is to a great extent due to her secondments and sabbaticals at both industrial and academic institutions. Indeed, many of her key scientific achievements came about as a result of these.

During her 23 years at UCL, Nina spent 24 months with BP Oil and BP Chemicals, sponsored by a Royal Society Industry Fellowship, EPSRC and BP; six weeks as an academic visitor to Lund Institute of Technology, Department of Automatic Control; near nine months on sabbatical leave at University of Alberta, Department of Chemical and Materials Engineering; three weeks in Japan funded by the Royal Society, including a work experience in the control engineering office at Mitsui Chemicals Omuta factory; and six months as an academic visitor to ABB Norway Corporate Research Centre, funded by the Royal Academy of Engineering Global Research Award and ABB.

Then, while at Imperial College London and already the ABB/Royal Academy of Engineering Chair of Process Automation, Nina had two secondments and a final sabbatical leave at ABB Corporate Research Center in Poland.

Unconventionally, when Nina commenced her part-time PhD in 2001, she had already done a significant amount of research at UCL and the above industrial and academic institutions, and she had in fact already obtained her full Professorship at UCL. Mick Flanagan at UCL was the official supervisor but in reality Nina completed this at the very highest of standards by herself.

As a Person

As evidenced by all the contributions assembled here, Nina has marked her students, peers and friends with the integrity she treated these relationships with. When talking of Nina, humility and kindness are qualities that immediately stand in everyone's mind. Visibly her priorities stood with ensuring good

mentoring and people development, being professional with her colleagues, welcoming all ideas, and accommodating individual constraints.

About this Festschrift

There are many ways to celebrate the achievements of academic excellence. Discussing the format amongst the editors and with colleague Alexander Fay at Helmut-Schmidt-University in Hamburg, it quickly became evident that the traditional format of a special edition in one of the journals Nina publishes in would not be the right format. We wanted to ensure that everyone would be able to contribute. ABB colleagues Alf Isaksson confirmed that collaborators and friends from industry, may not have been interested in writing a scientific article.

We also believe that Nina's workings impacted not only in her contributions to research but also on a personal level. Reading the articles by former and current students as well as former and current collaborators has confirmed this view.

The support from everyone in putting this Festschrift together has been overwhelming. The call for papers was passed around the University of Alberta through Sirish Shah and Biao Huang, at ABB, at Eastman Chemical Company and around the UK. Without the help of your colleagues at Imperial College, Claire Adjiman, Benoit Chachuat, Nilay Shah and Senait Selassie this Festschrift would not have been possible.

The contributions are ordered according to chronological events in Nina's life to our best ability. There are 41 contributions by 60 colleagues.

Dear Nina, you have given so many people so much over the years. Your influence as an educator, mentor, colleague, friend and role model is difficult to express in exact measures. The best way is most likely to read the contributions here - and extrapolate because despite best efforts we were sure not able to track every person down.

We wish you all the best for your retirement and many fun filled days.

Margret Bauer, Moncef Chioua and Inês Cecílio

Johannesburg (ZA), Ladenburg (DE) and Cambridge (UK)

5. December 2019